

D3.2 – Report on mechanical properties of materials

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Executive summary

Proton-conducting ceramic tubular membranes have been characterized via a four-point bending technique to assess their linear behaviour and mechanical properties. Different testing conditions have been investigated, varying parameters such as temperature, gas atmosphere composition and time of exposure to the latter conditions to determine the effect of relevant operating parameters on the mechanical reliability of the aforementioned components.

The tests were conducted in air at room temperature and in reducing conditions at 650°C upon short-term exposure and 1000 hours of ageing in the same atmosphere and temperature.

The tubular proton-conducting ceramic membranes showed satisfactory mechanical performance in all the conditions mentioned above. A mild decrease in the mechanical properties can be observed upon exposure to higher temperatures due to softening of the metallic phase present in the support and reduced fracture resistance. Long-term exposure to reducing conditions at high temperatures did not induce any further reduction in the mechanical performance, indicating that no evident degradation phenomena affected the microstructure and chemical characteristics of the specimens. This finding was further confirmed by microstructural and chemical characterization.

It can be concluded that the tubular membranes object of this study ensure satisfactory mechanical reliability and are not affected by significant degradation phenomena in the investigated conditions.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Presentation of WINNER

The WINNER project aims to develop an efficient and durable technology platform based on electrochemical proton conducting ceramic (PCC) cells designed for unlocking a path towards commercially viable production, extraction, purification and compression of hydrogen at small to medium scale. This will be demonstrated in WINNER in three applications: ammonia cracking, dehydrogenation of hydrocarbons, and reversible steam electrolysis. By such, WINNER will create innovative solutions for flexible, secure and profitable storage and utilization of energy in the form of hydrogen and green ammonia, electrification of the chemical industry and sectors coupling.

The WINNER project builds on the pioneering multidisciplinary expertise of world leading partners in the fields of proton conducting ceramic (PCC) materials and technologies to combine materials science, multi-scale multi-physics modelling and advanced in-situ and operando characterisation methods to unveil unprecedented performance of tubular PCC cells assembled in a flexible multi-tube module operating at industrially relevant conditions. WINNER will develop innovative cell architectures with multifunctional electrodes and a novel pressure-less current collection system using eco-friendly and scalable manufacturing routes.

Figure 1 WINNER concept focusing on novel materials, electrodes, current collection, and assemblies for three main applications

The experimental activities will be steered by a novel multi-scale multi-physics modelling platform and enhanced experimentation methodologies. These tools combined with advanced operando and in situ methods will serve at establishing correlations between performance and degradation mechanisms associated with both materials properties and interface's evolution upon operation. Testing of cells and modules will also be conducted to define performance and durability in various operation modes. Techno-economic assessment of the novel PCC processes will be conducted as well as Life Cycle Assessment. The project is coordinated by SINTEF with support from University of

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Oslo, Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC-ITQ), Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU), Aktiebolaget Sandvik Materials Technology, CoorsTek Membrane Sciences AS, ENGIE, Shell Global Solutions International B.V.

1.2 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable aims to report on the mechanical properties of tubular half-cells composed of a Ni-BaCe_{0.2}Zr_{0.7}Y_{0.1}O_{3-δ} fuel electrode support and BaCe_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}Y_{0.1}O_{3-δ} electrolyte (Ni-BCZY27/BCZY18) and on the methodologies adopted for the determination of the latter characteristics. Section 2 provides a description of the objective of the investigation and the methodologies applied to determine the aforementioned properties. Section 3 summarizes the results of the experimental activity.

2 Determination of mechanical properties

2.1 Objective

The mechanical strength and elastic properties of the components can strongly affect the reliable operation of electrochemical devices such as proton-conducting ceramic cells (PCCCs). During operation, a multiplicity of stresses are generated in PCCCs, related to phenomena like applied pressure gradients, lattice chemical expansion due to hydration, thermal expansion mismatch between the various components and non-uniform temperature distribution. Consequently, it is fundamental to determine the mechanical behavior of such devices in relevant operating conditions in terms of atmospheres and temperatures to ensure their reliability and further development of their mechanical performance.

The mechanical behavior of the aforementioned devices can be generally described via parameters such as:

- Elastic modulus (**E**): measure of the resistance to the elastic (i.e. recoverable) deformation of an object upon application of a stress;
- Poisson's ratio (**ν**): ratio between axial and transversal deformation upon application of a uniaxial compressive stress;
- Tensile strength (**σ₀**): maximum tensile stress before failure;
- Weibull probability of failure (**P_f**): Statistical probability of rupture of the tested sample upon application of a tensile stress;
- Weibull modulus (**m**): dimensionless parameter which describes variability in the measured material strength of brittle materials;

The work described in this report aimed to determine the parameters above in different operating conditions and to use them as inputs for a finite element model that could describe the stress field and probability of failure of proton conducting ceramic devices based on a tubular cell geometry in relevant conditions. The aforementioned model would provide valuable information for the fabrication of reliable devices and could be applied to components with different material compositions.

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2.2 High throughput four-point bending methodology

The tubular samples received from CoorsTek Membrane Sciences AS were tested via a high throughput four-point bending technique in order to investigate the elastic properties of the proton-conducting ceramic half-cells of standard compositions in different atmospheres and temperatures.

The tubular half-cells were initially cut along the axis to obtain two semi-tubular specimens, which were then measured to determine their dimensions in terms of thickness of the membrane, width, height and length.

Different testing conditions were identified to determine the effects of relevant operating temperatures and gas atmospheres. The following testing conditions were selected:

- In air at room temperature;
- In reducing conditions (5% H₂ in N₂) at 650°C;
- In reducing conditions (5% H₂ in N₂) at 650°C after exposure to the latter atmosphere and temperature for 1000 h;

The ageing processes took place in a tubular furnace, and the heating cycle, both for the ageing procedures and the tests at high temperature, was based on a heating and cooling rate of 90°C. For each testing condition, approximately 30 specimens were analyzed in order to ensure the statistical reliability of the analysis.

Four-point bending tests were carried out through a piece of equipment that allows testing of multiple specimens in a single heating cycle while ensuring control of temperature, heating and cooling rate and composition of the gas atmosphere. The equipment is composed of a furnace, a gas supply system and a four-point bending fixture in which the loading pins are connected to an actuator while the support pins are part of a rocking lever connected to load cells. The load cells register the load applied to the samples, while the actuator allows determining the imposed displacement. The registered data consist of load-displacement curves. Figure 2 shows the four-point bending testing equipment and a fractured sample after testing.

Analysis of the load-displacement data allowed the determination of the elastic modulus and stress at fracture for the different specimens. Moreover, a statistical analysis of the data was carried out to determine the tensile strength, Weibull modulus and probability of failure of the tested components.

Among the samples tested in various conditions, multiple fractured specimens were characterized via X-ray Diffractometry (XRD) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) in order to assess their fracture mode, microstructural characteristics and possible generation of undesired secondary phases upon exposure to the ageing and test conditions.

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Figure 2: a) Overview of the high through-put four-point bending equipment; b) Fractured sample after testing.

3 Results

3.1 Mechanical properties of Ni-BCZY27/BCZY18 tubular half cells

Table 1 summarizes the results of the four-point bending tests carried out in the different testing conditions. Figure 3 shows the Weibull strength distribution of the specimens tested in the different conditions.

Table 1: Summary of mechanical testing results.

Specimen denomination	Test conditions	Number of tested samples	Tensile strength, σ_0 [MPa]	Weibull Modulus, m	Elastic Modulus, E [GPa]
HCRT	20°C in air	27	241.6	15.3	98.6
HCHT	5% H ₂ in N ₂ at 650°C	30	159	11.1	70.9
HCAS	5% H ₂ in N ₂ at 650°C after 1000 h ageing	26	149	12.5	72

As clearly observable from the data in Table 1, exposure to high temperatures and reducing atmospheres causes a reduction in the mechanical strength of the samples. Moreover, the samples exposed to the above conditions presented a lower elastic modulus and Weibull modulus. On the other hand, no clear difference can be observed between the mechanical performance of specimens tested at high temperature with and without being exposed to long-term ageing procedures in reducing conditions, indicating the absence of evident degradation phenomena taking place upon long-term exposure to the aforementioned conditions.

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Figure 3: Weibull strength distribution of Ni-BCZY27/BCZY18 specimens tested at: a) room temperature in air (■), b) 650°C in reducing conditions (●), c) high temperature in reducing conditions after 1000 hours of ageing in the same atmosphere at 650°C (▲).

3.2 Characterization of Ni-BCZY27/BCZY18 tubular membranes

In order to assess the factors affecting the mechanical performance of the tubular proton-conducting ceramic membranes, multiple samples tested in the conditions mentioned above underwent characterization via SEM and XRD.

Figure 4 shows micrographs of samples fractured in the different testing conditions, while Figure 5 shows XRD spectra of the fracture samples.

Analysis of the microstructure of samples belonging to the sets HCRT, HCHT and HCAS shows that no evident degradation phenomena occurred upon exposure to high temperatures and reducing conditions. The grain size of both ceramic and metallic phases does not show any clear difference, and the specimens appear to have fractured via intergranular fracture mode.

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Figure 4: Micrographs of fractured surfaces of samples a) tested at room temperature in air, b) tested in 5% H_2/N_2 at 650°C and c) aged for 1000 hours at 650°C in 5% H_2/N_2 and tested in the latter conditions.

Figure 5: XRD patterns of samples tested at room temperature in air and samples aged in reducing conditions at 650°C for 1000 hours and tested in an analogous environment.

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Analogously, the XRD spectra of HCRT, HCHT, and HCAS samples do not indicate the generation of undesired secondary phase upon short and long-term exposure to reducing conditions at 650°C.

It can be concluded that the inferior mechanical performance of the HCHT and HCAS samples compared to the HCRT specimens can be related to a reduced fracture resistance and a softening of the ductile nickel phase rather than to degradation phenomena, in good agreement with the findings of the mechanical testing procedures.

4 Conclusions

The investigation of the mechanical properties of proton-conducting ceramic tubular membranes has been carried out via four-point bending. The tests were carried out in different gas atmospheres and temperatures and also involved samples aged at high temperatures in reducing conditions for 1000 hours.

The specimens tested at room temperature in air showed satisfactory mechanical properties in terms of tensile strength and Weibull modulus. Upon exposure to high temperatures in reducing conditions, the Weibull parameters and elastic moduli of the specimens showed a slight decrease. However, no apparent signs of degradation can be identified in the mechanical performance of the samples to the aforementioned conditions for 1000 hours, indicating that no evident chemical and microstructural degradation phenomena occurred during the ageing procedures.

Microstructural and chemical characterization of the fractured samples supported the findings of the mechanical characterization, showing the absence of any evident degradation phenomena. The decreased Weibull parameters and elastic moduli of the samples tested at 650°C in reducing conditions upon short and long-term exposure compared to the samples tested in air at room temperature can be attributed to a reduced fracture resistance of the ceramic phase and a softening of the ductile metallic phase.

It can be concluded that the specimens presented a satisfactory mechanical performance in all the testing conditions considered in this work and that the proton-conducting membranes object of this investigation ensure long-term mechanical reliability.